

NON-ATTAINABILITY OF THE EXPECTED ALLELE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM AT A SINGLE LOCUS

(APPENDIX TO: “ESTIMATING RECOMBINATION USING ONLY THE ALLELE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM”)

DANIEL A. RICKERT AND MATTHEW W. HAHN

INTRODUCTION

Suppose we have a diploid population with a large constant effective population size, N_e , and a constant mutation rate, μ , per locus per generation. We assume that after scaling time in units of $2N_e$ generations, the gene tree, G , giving the relationship among $n \ll N$ sampled individuals at a particular locus, is modeled by the standard neutral coalescent [2], with mutations falling on the resulting gene tree at rate $\frac{\theta}{2}$, where $\theta = 4N_e\mu$.

We consider the random variable, ξ_i , representing the number of mutations that fall on a branch of G subtending exactly i tips. Throughout this note, we will assume an infinite-sites model of mutation, such that the allele frequency spectrum is given exactly by (ξ_1, \dots, ξ_n) . It is known [1] that

$$(1) \quad \mathbb{E}[\xi_i] = \frac{\theta}{i}.$$

Note that the expectation in Eq. (1) is with respect to both the randomness of the process that generates gene trees and the randomness of the mutation process on the gene trees. Here, we consider the case of the expected allele frequency spectrum conditional on a fixed gene tree, G . We demonstrate that for $n \geq 4$ sampled chromosomes (i.e. haploid samples), averaging over the randomness of the mutation process on G alone cannot lead to the non-conditional expected allele frequency spectrum:

$$(2) \quad \left(\mathbb{E}[\xi_1 | G], \dots, \mathbb{E}[\xi_{n-1} | G] \right) \neq \left(\frac{\theta}{1}, \dots, \frac{\theta}{n-1} \right).$$

In other words, the allele frequency spectrum generated at a single non-recombining locus can never match that generated by an infinite number of independent loci.

PROOF OF NON-ATTAINABILITY FOR 4 OR MORE TIPS

We fix $n \geq 4$, and consider a rooted, ultrametric, and binary gene tree G with n tips. For $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, let τ_i denote the total length of branches in G that subtend exactly i tips. Since mutations fall on the gene tree at rate $\frac{\theta}{2}$, we have that

$$(3) \quad \mathbb{E}[\xi_i | G] = \frac{\theta\tau_i}{2}.$$

To have any hope of obtaining the non-conditional allelic frequency spectrum, we need that all of τ_1, \dots, τ_n are nonzero. This is only possible if G has a “caterpillar” topology, in which the lineage subtending the most number of tips is involved in each coalescent event. We will therefore assume G has a caterpillar topology, with inter-coalescence times t_1, \dots, t_{n-1} as demonstrated in Figure 1. In order to ensure that G is binary, we will insist that t_1, \dots, t_{n-1} are positive. Under the coalescent model, the lengths τ_i are then given by

$$(4) \quad \tau_i = \begin{cases} nt_1 + \sum_{k=2}^{n-1} (n-k)t_k & i = 1 \\ t_i & i \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

FIGURE 1. A gene tree G with the caterpillar topology for $n = 5$ tips. Inter-coalescence times are given by t_1, \dots, t_4 .

We observe that the length τ_1 is greater than $(n - i)\tau_i$ for $2 \leq i \leq n - 1$. In particular, using the case $i = 2$, we see that the ratio of the first two terms in the conditional expected allele frequency spectrum is strictly less than that in the non-conditional expected allele frequency spectrum:

$$(5) \quad \frac{\mathbb{E}[\xi_2 | G]}{\mathbb{E}[\xi_1 | G]} = \frac{\tau_2}{\tau_1} < \frac{1}{n-2} \leq \frac{1}{2} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[\xi_2]}{\mathbb{E}[\xi_1]}.$$

Note that we used the assumption $n \geq 4$ in the middle of Eq. (5) to satisfy the inequality $\frac{1}{n-2} \leq 1/2$. The bound $n \geq 4$ is sharp: in the case $n = 3$, we may obtain the non-conditional expected allele frequency spectrum by taking G to have a caterpillar topology with inter-coalescence times $t_1 = \frac{1}{3}, t_2 = 1$, such that $\tau_1 = 2$ and $\tau_2 = 1$.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yun-Xin Fu. Statistical properties of segregating sites. *Theoretical Population Biology*, pages 172–197, 1995.
- [2] John Frank Charles Kingman. The coalescent. *Stochastic processes and their applications*, 13(3):235–248, 1982.

DEPARTMENT OF BIOLOGY AND DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, INDIANA UNIVERSITY, BLOOMINGTON, IN 47405